

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT VERBS

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Abstraction: In this article, we will study the characteristics of the verb

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What to do? What to be? A verb, comprising words that convey action and state in response to inquiries, plays a pivotal role in linguistic analysis.

Actions and states conveyed by verbs are attributed to specific individuals or objects, acting as the agents of these actions. Verbs are categorized into action verbs and state verbs based on their semantic functions.

Action verbs depict physical activities performed by individuals or objects, while state verbs articulate internal experiences of individuals and the transitional processes of objects. As previously mentioned, language and communication encompass five primary components: phonetics-phonology, morphology, lexicology, and syntax. In linguistic discourse, morphology and syntax collectively constitute grammar. In the subsequent discussion, we will delve into the domain of morphological studies.

Primarily, it is essential to address the grammatical structure of verbs. As one of the fundamental word categories, verbs distinguish themselves from other lexical groups through their syntactic function, grammatical form, and semantic significance.

In the literature, the following phenomena are described under the name “functional forms of the verb”:

1. Action name -sh, -v, -moq; run, enter, election, welcome, fear, drive, go, come
2. Adjective, go out + blood, cry + gan - fell
3. Speak in a friendly manner, come with respect, and greet with a smile.
4. (In some literature, a verb form with an adjective is added to these ranks under the name “pure verb”). These phenomena are called “functional form” because they adapt the verb to occur in a certain syntactic function. Actually, “adjustment to occurrence in the syntactic task” is an external feature of such formations. The creation of such forms first creates monad forms for its nouns, adjectives, and adverbs within the verb group. Due to the formation of such forms, the noun (substantive) form of the verb, the adjective (attributive) form, the adverbial (adverbial) form of the verb is formed, and fe It is possible to use the lexeme as a noun, as an adjective, as an adverb, the verb lexeme comes in the syntactic function of performing a noun lexeme through a noun form, an adjective lexeme through an adjective form, and an adverbial lexeme through an adverbial form. The most remarkable aspect is that the adverbial form serves to connect the verb lexeme to the verb lexeme in the function of a subordinate clause - determiner.
5. Verb forms that indicate the degree to which the executor participates in the process of action and state are considered relative forms. For example, in the verb sweep, the person

performing the sweeping action is definite, in the verb swept, it is indefinite, in the verb sweep, it is more than one, and in the verb sweep, it is expressed that the action was performed by another person.

6. Uzbek language has five relative forms. Relative adverbs are added after the base of the word and show who is doing the action.

7. In the definite article, the executor is definite and there is no additional participle in the main agreement.

8. Self-proportion in which the action performed is performed on itself and we can know it through its suffixes *-(i)n, -(i)l*, these suffixes are added depending on the last letter, depending on the vowel and consonant

9. The form of the verb expressing an action or state in which the executor of the passive participle is unknown is called the passive participle and has the additions *-(i)n, -(i)l*. The personal and passive participles are the same, but we can distinguish them depending on the subject. In the subjective case, the action is performed on itself, and in the passive case, the doer is unknown. *dressed - dressed*.

Cumulative ratio is a cumulative ratio when the work done by the worker or something is acquired by another person. *-t, -dir (-tir), -giz -kiz (-kiz), -gaz, -giz, -kaz, -kaz, -ir, -ar, -iz* are formed by such suffixes. *Rejoice, it's summer*

Several accusatives can be added to the base of the verb, which will increase the meaning of the word. It is added in the form *oqi, oqit, oqitir*, the basic meaning sounds stronger.

The joint relation is formed by adding the suffix *-ish* to the base of the verb, in which the action is performed by several people. *They planted trees for Nadir's father.*

Verbs can be connected with other words in a sentence and act as participles, possessives, complements, cases, and determiners. For this, the verb has special forms. The verb forms that are used to function as different parts of the sentence are considered the functional forms of the verb.

There are four task forms of verbs: 1) pure verb form (*read*); 2) action noun form (*to read, read*); 3) adjective form (*read, fluent*); 4) subjunctive form (*after reading and coming*).

The noun form of verbs is called action noun. Action nouns take possessive, accusative, and plural suffixes like nouns, and act as clauses that they perform in a sentence. For example: *Learn to write beautifully! Your writing is not bad.* It is formed by adding suffixes *-ish (sh), moq, mak* to the base of the verb. *Yasha+sh*

The adjective form of the verb is called an adjective. Adjectives to verb bases *-gan (-kan, -kan), -yeda (-adigan), -(a)yotgan, -(a)r*

it is formed by adding additions. Adjectives are similar to adjectives in that they denote persons and things. Adjectives represent a stable, stable sign of a person and thing, while adjectives represent a sign of change and movement. *Big (adjective) river, flowing (adjective) river.* Adjectives, being a form of a verb, express the meanings of tense, participle, and proportion.

Verbal form of the verb is called verbative.

Verbs are similar to verbs in that they denote action. *Ravishdosh* is also attached to a verb like *ravish* and indicates its sign. *He came on foot (ravish), he came in a hurry (ravishdosh).* *-(i)b, -a-y* forms mostly indicate the state of the action, sometimes the time, the reason, *-gancha (-chancha, -chancha)* form state, *-gach, (-kach, -kach), -guncha (-kuncha, -kuncha)* means the

moment, -gani (-kani, -kani, -gali) means the purpose of the form. Through these forms, we can learn the internal forms of the verb word group.

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